

Health Psychology Relation to Providing Psycho-Psychiatric Care to Persons with the Case of COVID – 19

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Abstract

Overall, the research illuminates some fascinating patterns that have arisen over the course of the field's evolution over the last four decades as well as some interesting scientific hypotheses that may help us understand mental health and wellbeing better. First, throughout the last several decades, especially the last ten, there has been a marked increase in interest in the mental health and wellbeing of college students. This pattern indicates that the sector has not yet achieved maturity and will continue to grow in the coming years. Second, the study on this topic is mostly interdisciplinary and the outcome of research in a variety of subfields that fall under the broad heading of behavioral and biological sciences. Finally, a group of accomplished scholars, largely from various regions of the globe, developed the research on this subject. As a result, the discipline will be shaped by a new generation of researchers for many years to come. In the realm of mental health, researchers have recently had access to a broad range of study subjects. Positive mental

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health, mental illness, drug use, therapy, stigma, stress, and measuring mental health are a few of these topics. The results of this study also highlighted a number of problems that could be impeding the growth of research into college students' mental health and overall wellbeing. For instance, present research often places an excessive emphasis on the theoretical and disciplinary approaches that have developed in affluent nations. Additional study is required to provide a better and more accurate picture of the situation and to ensure that all points of view are appropriately represented, especially from low- and middle-income nations and emerging economies. The results of this study will help practitioners and administrators improve and broaden current efforts and programs that support mental health and wellbeing in higher education settings. Due to their social and cultural beliefs, university students will be able to get different types of help. Also, the scientific community that supports the expansion of the area is widely spread.

Keywords: *COVID – 19, Psycho-Psychiatric Care, Health and Psychology, Psychological Health*

Introduction

There are various working groups, however there is little cross-group research cooperation due to the geographical, cultural, and language disparities among these groups. The closeness of these elements tends to limit these correlations at the global level. In this regard, further initiatives like the WMH-ICS Initiative may be able to partially address this issue by fostering information exchange within regions and growing national and international research partnerships. Moreover, special issues of important journals in the area that welcome cross-cultural study on the topic might support regional research cooperation as well as research in underrepresented nations. An increase in study in the social sciences and humanities that examines how social, cultural, economic, and educational factors affect how mental health and well-being are conceptualized, manifested, and experienced would be beneficial to the field as a whole. It is important to do more study in fields like sociology, anthropology, business, and education. This will probably make ideas about good mental health more permeable and help to advance salutogenic methods in studies of university students' mental health and wellbeing. There are many problems with this study. The WoS database was the sole source for the papers, which significantly constrained how far the findings could be applied. Second, WoS has a disproportionately large number of papers published in

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English and provides more thorough coverage of disciplines including engineering, biomedical sciences, and life sciences (Mongeon and Paul-Hus, 2016). This may contribute to explaining, at least in part, the comparatively low number of publications in the present study for research in the social sciences, the arts, and humanities, as well as in nations where English is not the native tongue.

Eventually, only publications discovered in scholarly journals were gathered and examined. Reviews, book chapters, and conference proceedings were thus disregarded. In order to give a different scope of research, the results of this study may be duplicated in following studies utilizing various databases (such as Scopus and PubMed) or a combination of these databases, as well as various search criteria. Notwithstanding this, we believe that the bibliometric approach utilized in this research offers fresh insights on the history, present state, and certain roadblocks to the subject's advancement.

The goal of our study is to better understand how the COVID-19 pandemic has affected society's psychological well-being and mental health, as well as how to treat individuals with post-COVID syndrome via telemedicine. The post-covid syndrome and the clinical manifestations of psychopathological symptoms in patients with this disease must be examined, as well as the effectiveness of appropriate treatment measures with the remote management of these patients using telemedicine technologies. It is crucial to establish a conceptual model for providing medical treatment via telemedicine to patients with COVID-19 disease.

Method

Evaluate information from scientific literature about COVID-19's effects on mental health and the viability of utilizing telemedicine to provide patients psychological and psychiatric treatment. The study's fictitious hypothesis is that telemedicine is a useful method for giving distant psychological and psychiatric treatment to people with mental illness related with prior COVID-19 sickness. Review of the literature The COVID-19 coronavirus illness affects many facets of society globally, including both physical and mental health, directly and indirectly.

(a) create stress,

(b) despair and

(c) Don't generate anxiety.

It is possible to trace the origins of these impacts. This is objectively confirmed by the use of the IES-R and DASS, which are well recognized as trustworthy instruments for the diagnosis of depression, anxiety, and stress. Reliable procedures were used to perform these investigations. The probability of a post-COVID syndrome or the explanation for why these potential sequelae are indicated by such enduring symptoms are both supported by substantial data. Younger COVID-19 patients are more likely to have mental health issues; risk factors for these illnesses include being a woman, being jobless, and having concurrent chronic pathology.

Nonetheless, the psychological stress element of the global catastrophe brought on by the COVID-19 epidemic has been disregarded for far too long. The risk of sleeplessness, anxiety, depression, somatization, and obsessive-compulsive disorder among nurses, physicians, and other healthcare professionals is high¹⁹; however, boosting their social and psychological support has improved their psychological stability. The public's confidence in the functioning medical systems has declined throughout the pandemic.

Literature Study

Positive predictors of psychological quality of life and wellbeing were optimistic thinking, active dealing with stress, and social support, whereas negative predictors included perceived stress, sadness, anxiety, and sleeplessness. The psychological quality of life and well-being were shown to be favorably correlated with all of these characteristics.

(a) young age; female gender (but mental health also worsened in men, especially in the presence of chronic obstructive bronchopulmonary disease, up to the presence of suicidal thoughts);

(b) Higher self-esteem regarding the possibility of infection.

(c) Anxiety about psychological barriers and insecurity.

Several elements have been shown to influence the population's psychological condition during a pandemic. The central nervous system (CNS) has been shown to be directly and negatively

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affected by the coronavirus18, and the acute stress response that results from an epidemic situation is harmful in both the short- and long-term. The polymorphism of the psychopathological symptoms linked to COVID-19 and neuropsychological deficient processes should be taken into consideration when defining the differential diagnosis and treatment options.

The COVID-19 pandemic must be prevented from having a negative psychological impact by using a comprehensive strategy that considers psychological, social, and neurobiological variables. The necessity for psychological support and psychological help via the development of global psych preventive treatments and telemedicine has been elevated to priority due to the mental health crisis brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic. This is crucial since a fall in the number of persons seeking mental health care in hospitals is linked to apprehension about catching a communicable illness.

Remote mental health treatment has been developed as a result of the COVID-19 epidemic, but its execution requires access to reliable telecommunications and Internet services. Another strategy for delivering distant psychological and psychiatric treatment is to set up a telephone-based psychological support service.

Conversely, video platforms enable the evaluation of mental illnesses that are invisible on a phone. Positive outcomes from individuals with mental health issues utilizing COVID-19 demonstrate that this is the best course of action. It is crucial that the doctor takes steps to guarantee the therapeutic interaction is of the highest caliber and that the patient is secure and at ease when communicating with the therapist online. The doctor should simultaneously ensure that the patient is secure and at ease. Regulations that had impeded the growth of telemedicine, which has shown to be an effective and high-quality method of delivering medical care, were removed as a consequence of the difficulties in satisfying the population's health needs. The COVID-19 pandemic presents an opportunity to take use of telemedicine more, therefore allaying worries about its efficacy in the treatment of mental illness and demonstrating its efficacy. Psychotherapy delivery to patients has undergone significant cultural changes as a result of the COVID-19 epidemic, which are immediately reflected in virtual formats. This calls into question whether rules should be devised to guarantee the morally correct provision of care to patients at high risk.

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A kind of psychological and psychiatric assistance is telemedicine. Using tranquilizers and antidepressants from the non-benzodiazepine series, treatments for identified cases of anxiety, depression, and other emotional disorders of varying severity were conducted online in accordance with the cognitive-behavioral therapy protocol for generalized anxiety disorder and hypochondriac disorder.

Research Plan

The structure of the research project was based on the assumption that the following procedures would be carried out in the following order: Phase 1 involves the formulation of a problem statement as well as research goals and objectives. Phase 2 involves an analytical review of scientific literature resources on the problem of mental health disorders associated with COVID-19, as well as the provision of psychological and psychiatric care to patients in a telemedicine setting. Stage 3 involves the selection of valid research methods as well as the creation of a relevant sample. Phase 1 involves the formulation of a problem statement. Phase 2 involves an analytical review of scientific literature resources on the problem of mental health

At the first stage of the process, a problem description and research goals and objectives are formulated. At the second stage, there is an in-depth analysis of the scientific literature sources that are pertinent to the issue. The study is marred by several glaring deficiencies. Because we only surveyed patients who came to us independently for psychological and psychiatric help in a telemedicine setting, the sample size of the patients in the study was on the lower end of the spectrum than it could have been. This was because we only surveyed patients who came to us independently for help. This was one of the problems with the research that was done. It is the purpose of this project to continue research to locate probable subclinical instances of post-covid syndrome. Outcomes Patients who can recover from COVID-19 on their own are characterized by memory, sleep, and appetite disturbances; decreased mood and ability to work; loss of hope and interest in life; anxiety and fear of death; hypochondriac disorders; and obsessive-compulsive symptoms confirmed by clinical and psychopathological research; in addition, patients worry for their loved ones. Individuals who were recuperating from COVID-19 also exhibited symptoms like obsessive and compulsive behaviors.

Results

The acute phase of COVID-19 was manifested to varied degrees in the individuals that were evaluated, and the severity of the illness was defined by the existence of premorbid chronic bronchopulmonary and immunodeficiency pathology rather than by gender and age. Instead of considering factors such as gender and age, the severity of the illness was evaluated based on the existence of premorbid chronic bronchopulmonary and immunodeficiency pathology.

In addition, nearly one third of the patients who were checked did not exhibit any evidence of having their sense of smell affected in any way. It is also important to note that, according to the findings of a retrospective analysis of the patients' mental health and behavioral histories before the onset of COVID-19, none of the patients had a clinically significant mental health problem or personality and behavioral disorder prior to the infection. This indicates that they were in a relatively good state of health prior to the distribution of COVID-19 and that they did not seek the assistance of psychiatrists or medical psychologists in the past.

Measures of Weak Well-Being Alongside Activity and Mood

All of them had low levels of well-being, as well as activity and mood, which had a close correlation with the findings of earlier evaluations. The decrease in activity and mood was expressed more than the health status, indicating the presence of both anxiety-depressive and hypochondriac symptoms, which was also detected during clinical and psychopathological investigations. Symptoms of hypochondria are characterized by an exaggerated fear of illness or injury. Exaggerated worry about being sick or hurt is one of the hallmarks of hypochondria, which may manifest itself in a variety of ways. In addition to this treatment, a medication therapy consisting of antidepressants and tranquilizers that did not include benzodiazepines was administered. The results of a second investigation provided independent confirmation for the conclusions of the first study. [Case in point:] [Case in point:]

- (a) 1-normal,
- (b) 2-light,
- (c) 3-medium,
- (d) 4 - severe,

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- (e) 5 - extremely severe.
- (f) 1 - before treatment,
- (g) 2 - post treatment,
- (h) 3 - follow

It was feasible for the patients who were assessed to attain normalization of their indicators on the depression scale as a consequence of the therapy that they received. This is the inference that one is able to make by looking at the figure. Patients who were diagnosed with a severe form of COVID-19 and who also suffered from concomitant premorbid chronic bronchopulmonary pathology were found to be more likely to experience long-term psychopathological symptoms as well as somatic post-covid complications. These somatic post-covid complications included myocarditis, renal dysfunction, and other similar conditions.

When combined with antidepressants and tranquilizers that do not contain benzodiazepines, the therapeutic intervention based on cognitive-behavioral therapy protocols for hypochondriac and generalized anxiety disorder was found to be effective in the treatment of mental disorders in patients, according to the findings of our study, which also included a follow-up period. This result is significant for the treatment of mental problems, particularly in those who suffer from COVID-19 disease. According to the results of this study, chronic pre-illness disruptions of the bronchopulmonary and immunological systems act as predecessors not only to the development of long-term psychopathological symptoms but also to the onset of post-COVID somatic difficulties in the patient.

Patients diagnosed with post-covid syndrome were the focus of our research as we built a theoretical framework for the delivery of psychological and psychiatric therapy through telemedicine. The development of this model, which can be shown in Figure 6, included reviewing and summarizing the findings of the study in order to determine how they compared to the data that was discovered in the scholarly literature. The significance of this paradigm may be broken down into four distinct categories, which are the psychodiagnostics, the psychotherapeutic, the psychopharmacotherapeutic, and the psychoprophylactic categories, respectively. The clinical picture and characteristics of the progression of the post-covid syndrome in each patient are what determine

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the sequence in which the blocks of this model are completed, and there is a close connection between all of the individual blocks. At the same time, the psychodiagnostics unit includes dynamically monitoring the patient's condition at all stages of the provision of medical and preventive care, utilizing not only the clinical and psychopathological method, but also pathopsychological diagnosis. This is done in conjunction with the provision of medical and preventive care. In addition to the clinical and psychopathological procedure, this is also done. The psychoprophylaxis block treats the condition throughout all its phases, including the medical-psychological and medical-social rehabilitation stages. This model was established with the concepts of bioethics and the moral duty of the attending physician in mind. Its primary emphasis is on the individual patient, and it was done so with those considerations in mind.

On the basis of the data that we collected; we identified a particular case of asthenic post-covid syndrome. Patients with post-covid syndrome have a slower recovery from cognitive impairments than patients with protracted asthenic symptoms, as well as symptoms of anxiety and sadness, which may be related. When coming up with solutions for treatment and rehabilitation to treat patients afflicted with such diseases, this facet of the situation really has to be taken into consideration.

Argument

The results of our research provide credence to the assertions made by other scientists within the scientific community, namely that COVID-19 is associated with adverse effects on the central nervous system. The condition known as COVID-19 is distinguished by the presence of psychopathological symptoms, which can take the form of manifestations of an anxiety-depressive syndrome with varying degrees of severity, cognitive dysfunction, and other phenomena that continue for a significant amount of time after the disease has been cured. Cognitive impairment, anxiety-depressive syndrome of varied severity¹⁹⁻²¹, and other problems that endure long after they are gone are examples of these symptoms.

Anxiety, panic attacks, and mental health conditions such as post-traumatic stress disorder, hypochondriac syndrome, and anxiety-depressive syndrome may all contribute to panic attacks (PTSD) Cognitive impairment (memory and attention impairment) and emotional problems are

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also related with asthenic post-covid syndrome (anxiety-depressive syndrome, stress and panic responses). Hypochondriac symptoms are classic indicators of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). We recommend using a valid set of psychodiagnostics tests, which consists of the following methods, to objectify the clinical and psychopathological manifestations of post-covid syndrome in telemedicine when it is difficult to observe the patient in person. This can be done using telemedicine.

“to measure the level of anxiety, depression and stress; Distinguish between personal and situational concerns”

According to the results of Spielberger and Khanin, chronic pre-illness disruptions of the bronchopulmonary and immunological systems are predictors of the existence of long-term psychopathological symptoms as well as the prevalence of post-COVID somatic issues. [Citation needed] The cognitive-behavioral therapy protocols for hypochondriac and generalized anxiety disorder should serve as a model for the treatment techniques that should be used for individuals suffering from post-Covid mental health issues. The treatment plan for these individuals should also include the administration of non-benzodiazepine antidepressants and tranquilizers. When there is a prolonged decrease in anxiety and depressive symptoms, an improvement in patients' well-being, and an increase in both their activity and mood, there is evidence that such an intervention has an elevated level of therapeutic effectiveness. The therapy of mental illnesses in post-covid syndrome has been proven to have a beneficial long-term prognosis, according to studies that followed patients after treatment. This demonstrates that the use of telemedicine to give psychological and mental treatment to patients coping with the effects of COVID-19 illness is successful. While designing the conceptual patient-centered model that we devised for delivering psycho-psychiatric therapy to patients with post-covid syndrome using telemedicine, we made sure to keep bioethical principles and the moral obligation of the treating physician in mind.

The model consists of four semantic blocks:

- (a) *psychodiagnostic,*
- (b) *psychotherapeutic,*

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- (c) *psychopharmacotherapeutic and*
- (d) *psychosocial.*

In order to give psycho-psychiatric therapy to patients suffering from post-covid syndrome via the use of telemedicine, we devised a paradigm that is focused on the patient.

An example in the form of a schematic showing the mental issues that are related with post-covid syndrome Those who have been diagnosed with post-covid syndrome may gain something by participating in psychological and mental treatment sessions that are conducted through telemedicine.

In the past, the major focus of many therapists was on the symptoms and challenges connected with mental health disease, specifically how to heal "issues." This was because many therapists believed that these were the key areas in which patients might be helped. There has been a shift in the focus of therapy for mental health away from individual factors like motivation, positive thinking, happiness, and emotional resilience, and toward the symptoms of mental illness as they are manifested in the life of a person. This shift came about as a result of an increased awareness of the importance of these factors. A pioneer in the field of positive psychology named George Vaillant (2009) made the observation that older research papers on psychiatry and mental health contain many discussions of anxiety, depression, stress, anger, and fear, but very little about compassion. Vaillant was one of the first people to work in the field of positive psychology.

The finding that Vaillant made was a reaction to the fact that the previous study studies had a tendency to concentrate more on negative emotions than they do on good ones. There has been a considerable change in the focus placed on both the work that is done in the area of mental health as well as therapeutic practice as a direct result of the advent of positive psychology. In the field of positive psychology, feelings of contentment and overall well-being are seen as "essential human qualities" (Davidson et al., 2005). The study of positive psychology has made it easier to comprehend the means by which we are able to cultivate our own internal capabilities and make the most of the time we have at our disposal. Positive psychology is sometimes referred to as "the study of ordinary talents and virtues" because, in contrast to symptomatic therapy and treatment, it places an emphasis on maintaining emotional balance, effectively managing expectations, and

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engaging in fruitful thought. In the 1960s and 1970s, researchers in the United States pioneered the field of positive psychology (Sheldon & King, 2001). The area of positive psychology functions as a complementary modality to more conventional methods for the treatment of mental health disorders. In the following paragraphs, we shall investigate the connection between positive psychology and a person's overall psychological well-being. Before we go any further, we thought it may be good to give you with a website where you can download three positive psychology exercises for free. You'll find the link at the bottom of this article. Participating in these scientifically based activities will provide you with the knowledge and skills necessary to enhance the health and happiness of your clients, pupils, or staff. They place an emphasis on fundamental aspects of positive psychology, such as an individual's strengths, values, and capacity for self-compassion.

Although though people in colonial America did not recognize alcoholism as an illness at the time, this does not mean that alcoholism was not a contributing factor to the high morbidity rate in the 18th century. During the course of the last several years, empirical underpinnings for each of the six models have been readily accessible, which is an essential point to bring out. To begin, one approach to understanding mental health is to think of it as a condition that is either superior to the usual state or an objectively desirable mental state, such as the capacity to labor or love. Second, positive psychology is one way to think about mental health. Maslow's concept of "self-actualizing" is an early example of this approach, and it serves as an example of this style of thinking. In conclusion, maturity may be seen as synonymous with sound mental health when viewed from the viewpoint of the growth of individuals who possess good mental health. The fourth point is that one's mental health may be analyzed in terms of one's emotional or social quotient. Last but not least, one might consider one's own "subjective well-being" while thinking about mental health. It is a mental state that may be experienced by an individual in their own mind as feelings of pleasure, satisfaction, and desire.

In conclusion, mental health may be seen as resilience, which can be described as the ability for efficient adaptation and equilibrium. In other words, mental health can be understood as homeostasis. After giving it some consideration, it's become abundantly evident that each of these models can only explain a tiny portion of the "elephant," which is mental health. To evaluate if the

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characteristics of each model are additive or not, one of the objectives of the work that will be done in the future should include the use of multivariate modeling and should be supported by empirical data.

Excellent psychological health in Comparison to the Typical In the year 1835, Adolphe Quetelet is credited with writing what is widely regarded as the first significant book on normalcy. Instead of concentrating on illness, he looked for a "more direct approach to what is good and lovely" (p. x), and his ultimate objective was to do statistical research on healthy individuals.

Up to the period of World War II, Quetelet's challenge to physicians working in the field of mental health was often ignored. In 1941, the board that was responsible for the draft in the United States sought out health specialists to define mental health. The assignment that they were given was one that had never been completed before.

During World War II preliminary research on normal adaptive behavior was conducted for the first time. It was not released until well after the end of the Second World War. This kind of study has concentrated on investigating the adaptability of healthy or normal populations from a variety of vantage points. Despite this, many well-known psychiatrists who practiced after World War II concur with Freud, who disregarded mental wellness as an "ideal creation." Lewis contended in the late 1950s that "mental health is an incredibly illusive phrase," while Redlich made the following assertions in the same decade:

"We do not have a statistically or clinically comprehensive definition of normality and mental health"

Shortly thereafter, Jahoda's report to the Joint Commission on Mental Illness and Health led to a change in basic assumptions in healthcare. According to Jahoda's theory, a person whose mental state is healthy.

- 1) *be in touch with their own identity and feelings.*
- 2) *being future-oriented and productively connected to life.*
- 3) *have a spirit that provides resistance to stress.*

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- 4) *have autonomy, perceive reality without distortion, and yet have empathy and*
- 5) *being able to work, love, play and be productive in problem solving.*

That is a clear demonstration of Jahoda's idea. Even though the objective of Jahoda's study was to clear up the "vague, unclear, and ambiguous connotation" connected with the phrase "mental health," Jahoda was unable to compile sufficient factual data to prove that he was in the right. The probable definition was significantly different from the standard one. The earliest empirical research on mental health was conducted in the 1960s, starting with the study of "homicides" (physical education departments chosen for normalcy) by Grinker et al. and the study of normality by Offer and Sabshin. Both studies were conducted in the same decade. The first longitudinal study of positive mental health to harvest is arguably the qualifying process that led to the selection of a healthy person for an important role, who had been eliminated for resilience for more than a decade. While data from the Terman Study at Stanford, the Human Development Institute at Berkeley (24, 25), and the Adult Development Study at Harvard will be quite informative later, the first longitudinal study of positive mental health to harvest is arguably the qualifying process that led to the selection of a healthy person for an important role. The findings of this study shed light on the necessity of preserving one's mental health as well as the intrinsic logic for doing so.

An early research in mental health that had a significant influence on the profession was called the Menninger Psychotherapy Experiment. Lester Luborsky, a psychologist at Menninger, devised an experimental mental health measure called the Health-Disease Rating Scale. This scale, which has a range from 0 to 100 and is used to assess the psychological functioning of study participants, is termed the Health-Disease Rating Scale. In 1976, two of the DSM-creators III's renamed the Health-Disease Rating Scale to the Global Assessment Scale after making modifications to the scale (GAS). This was done since Luborsky's scale was developed more for the purpose of evaluating candidates for psychotherapy than for broad epidemiological investigations. Because of this, the Health-Disease Rating Scale received a new moniker. The range of reliability values that were obtained for inter-rater agreement for each instrument as well as agreement amongst the tools was found to be between 0.85 and 0.95. Armelius and his colleagues discovered, after analyzing the differences between the two distinct cultures, that "the use of the Health-Illness

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Rating Scale as a mental health thermometer internationally has been substantially validated." As an updated version of the GAS, the GAF Scale was first published in the DSM-III-R handbook. It is also referred to by its previous name, Axis V. There is no one indicator that can be used to define someone's mental health, similar to how there is no one metric that can represent greatness in the decathlon; yet all of these indicators are intimately connected to each other. On the Health-Disease Rating Scale, a score between 95 and 100 suggests "great functional integration," "resilience in the face of stress," "an optimum state of enjoyment and social engagement," and "excellent functional integration."

Secondly, the improvement of the GAF Scale and research into the validity of the GAF Scale across cultures would be beneficial to psychiatry. This will be to the advantage of the field. Second, since it is abundantly evident that preventing sickness is superior to treating it after it has already occurred, we need to investigate individuals who enjoy excellent mental health in the same way that agronomists investigate blight-resistant wheat and wheat that can withstand drought. Finally, the concept of mental health begs the issue of what kinds of therapeutic procedures are necessary in order to accomplish this goal. Which components of a person's mental health remain stable throughout time while others may be subject to transformation? For the same reason, even the most intensive educational intervention can only enhance IQ by around 7 points in most individuals, whereas persons who are utterly illiterate in Italian may become fluent speakers of the language with long-term therapeutic commitment. The medication clozapine or cognitive behavioral treatment may help enhance a score on the GAF Scale from 40 to 70; however, how can we increase a score from 70 to 90? This is a significant scientific subject that psychiatry has not yet started to examine, despite the fact that it is taking on an increasing amount of significance.

The purpose of positive psychology is to throw open the doors of "humanistic" psychology to scientific inquiry and practical application. At the individual level, it relates to positive individual characteristics such as love and professional capacity, courage, interpersonal skill, artistic sensitivity, perseverance, forgiveness, originality, future orientation, spirituality, high talent, and wisdom. At the collective level, it relates to high talent and wisdom. And in this pursuit of its best, positive psychology is not based on wishful thinking, belief, self-deception, fads, or waving; rather, it seeks to apply the best of the scientific method to the unique problems that human

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behavior presents to those who want to understand it in all its complexity. Moreover, in this pursuit of its best, positive psychology is not based on wishful thinking, belief, self-deception, fads, or waving; instead, it seeks to In addition, positive psychology does not rely its pursuit of excellence on wishful thinking, believing, self-deception, fads, or waving. Instead, it is founded on scientific research. In recent years, proponents of positive psychology have separated good mental health into four distinct aspects of the concept. Capabilities, facilitators, strengths, and results are all included in these component parts. The capacity to flourish in a certain subject is intrinsic, passed down through generations, and only marginally influenced by experience. Facilitators are a reflection of social interventions and environmental luck (for example, a stable family or a good school system); they are the kind of factors that may be modified experimentally in order to boost powers. The findings represent dependent elements (for example, a higher score on the GAF Scale, positive social interactions, and subjective well-being), which may be used as proof that doctors' efforts to strengthen their strengths are not merely wishful thinking. When it comes to their function as components of mental health, the precise ideal characteristics, also known as virtues, are the subject of much disagreement. The majority of individuals believe that it is important to have attributes such as knowledge, compassion, and the capacity to love and be loved by others. To counter this, do you believe that bravery ought to be counted as one of the strengths? If this is the case, then why not add brilliant, perfect musical pitch, and timely performance?

To begin, these are ideas that have been advocated for hundreds of years by individuals from a wide variety of time periods and civilizations all across the world. Second, one might value things not just as a means to a goal, but also in and of themselves, apart from the context in which they are used. There are flaws to be found in the subject of positive psychology. To get things started, the idealized depiction of mental health is one of the primary issues that decision-makers in the area of public health policy are concerned with. They are afraid that this viewpoint, which is held by a significant number of specialists working in the field of mental health, will make obtaining health insurance a difficult and expensive endeavor, but they do not want to admit this fact right immediately. Is it realistic to anticipate that any health insurance coverage would pay for therapies that assist patients in feeling more content with who they are as persons, and does this constitute a reasonable expectation? At some point in the future, society will be forced to make a decision on

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who is responsible for footing the cost for ensuring that individuals have good mental health: the individual, the school system, third-party payers, or religious groups; or some combination of the four. While considering positive psychology, a second aspect to take into account is the potential danger of prescribing culturally unsuitable local features. Making judgments about values exposes one to a considerable level of uncertainty. The terms "health" and "virtues," particularly the Aristotelian virtues, need to be distinguished from one another. Even if it's vital to keep wounds clean, that doesn't make it a virtue in and of itself. It is a commendable objective to maintain personal cleanliness in public places, yet doing so does not ensure one's health. The importance that positive psychology places on optimism is the third component of the field that has been called into doubt. Since the late 19th century, a significant number of social scientists, particularly those in Europe, have held the erroneous belief that optimistic cognition, and particularly religious optimism, is an incompatible "American" illusion that interferes with the accurate perception of reality. This mistaken belief has persisted despite the fact that it has been disproven time and again. In the early 20th century, this idea started to become widespread across Europe. Nietzsche, Freud, Marx, and Darwin all considered optimism to be evidence of a culturally immature stage of adolescence rather than a sign of adult mental health. These many philosophers are unanimously in agreement on this subject. Confronting oneself with the harsh truths of life is beneficial to one's health. In addition, a significant body of studies demonstrates that persons who are depressed have a more realistic outlook on the world. Cognitive therapists have shown over the last 30 years that modifying cognition not only changes behavior, but may also alter brain function. This connection between the two was previously unknown. Having said that, this is one of those things that can be altered. If someone who is depressed has a strong pattern of pessimism in their thinking, then someone who is mentally well seems to have a dominant pattern of optimism in their thinking. If a taught feeling of helplessness is a contributor to depression, then a learned sense of optimism and the capacity to deal with one's own issues should be among the most important components in ensuring one's mental health. One of the aspects that contributes to the significance of optimism in sustaining strong mental health is the fact that a statement like "the positive things that happen to me will endure forever" is one example of an optimistic statement. They may be found everywhere, and I am the one who first conceived of them. Chance has a role in the unfortunate events that occur to me, but their frequency is low, and they are not likely to recur. There are a lot

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of individuals who suffer from chronic depression who have an explanation that is totally different from what they wish to communicate. In addition to this, optimism incorporates hope, a component of psychological health that may be traced back to the tale of Pandora in Greek mythology.

Nonetheless, the idea of hope is one that psychiatry has not conducted much research on up until this point in time. Also, the illusion of optimism provides a person with the capacity to think about the future and prepare for it, rather than keeping the person from thinking about the future altogether. Research that has tracked participants over time has often demonstrated that having a plan for one's future is a key component of mental health. [Citation needed] [Citation needed] Lastly, positive psychology is the only model of mental health that even hints at how a GAF Scale score of 75 might be enhanced to a score of 90. This makes it a unique and important contribution to the field of mental health. Because of this, it stands apart from other models in the field of mental health.

Conclusion

Continuing to develop bridges with medicine and expanding on the work that underlies such humanistic principles with Meyer's "constructive experiment" are both part of the research agenda for positive psychology, which also includes other goals. The pursuit of knowledge encompasses both different kinds of activity. The brain, in contrast to other organs in the body, is designed to be pliable and may change in reaction to new experiences. This ability allows the brain to learn new things. The lungs and kidneys of a ten-year-old are more likely to reflect health than those of a fifty-year-old, but this is not the case with the central nervous systems of any of the age groups (CNS). So, at least in part, this continual development process is reflected in the mental health of adults today. It is arguable that "the brain" deteriorates with age; if this is the case, then why bother to grow the "mind"? Yet, research has revealed that even in the absence of sickness, the brain continues to work efficiently until the age of 80, and that it takes practically the whole of a person's lifespan for the brain to grow in a way that is neurologically optimum. According to prospective research, individuals have more emotional modulation and lower levels of depression when they are 70 years old as compared to when they are 30 years old.

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